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Positron emission tomography (PET) using 2-deoxy-2-[¹⁸F]fluoro-D-glucose (FDG) is effective for tumour staging, prognosis, and treatment monitoring, but its use is limited due to ionising radiation, making it unsuitable for frequent use and for certain populations like children and pregnant women. Deuterium Metabolic Imaging (DMI) is a chemical shift based spectroscopic imaging technique that is used to map the distribution of a deuterium-labelled metabolite and its metabolic fates in a biological sample or subject in an MRI scanner [1, 3]. In DMI, deuterium-labelled glucose ([6,6-D₂]D-glucose) has been administered to animals and humans mostly per os (but also intravenously in animals) and images of the metabolic fates of glucose such as lactate and glutamine/glutamate have been recorded [1]. Even though still limited in sensitivity (millimolar concentration), DMI can provide similar metabolic information as FDG-PET

Deuterated DDGs

Synthesis

Synthesis from a deuterated glucose

Deuterated D-glucose → [D]DG

Deuterated D-Glucose	DDG
D-Glucose-6,6-D ₂	[6,6-D ₂]DG
D-Glucose-D ₅	[D ₅]DG
D-Glucose-D ₇	[D ₇]DG
D-Glucose-D ₈	[D ₈]DG

Tedious synthesis, low yield

H/D exchange

[H]DG → D₂/D₂O → [D₄]DG

Catalyst

Flow Chemistry, mostly automated synthesis
D₂O recovery/re-enrichment for cost control
High yield

D-enrichment > 90%, Impurity: < 1% ethanol, Catalyst content < 1mg/kg
All 4DDG produced at few g scale

NMR Characterization (400 MHz)

Very good chemical purity (only trace amount of ethanol)
1H-1H couplings get simplified with higher number of hydrogens replaced by deuterons

¹³C

Very high D-enrichment in all DDGs
No visible impurity

MRSI @ 7 Tesla – phantom

CSI image acquired using the sequence optimized for in vivo experiments [4]

CSI-SSFP, TR/TE=16.4/1.2ms
Matrix 16X16, FOV 40X40 mm
64 spectral points, Acq.Time 18 min

[D₇]DDG produced a signal 3.5 x higher than [D₂]DDG

CSI signal was found to be quantitative: not only proportional to concentration, as previously verified, but also increased linearly with the number of deuterons per molecule

In vivo DDG Brain imaging

In vivo DDG brain imaging in a healthy mouse following intravenous administration (2 g/kg).

DDG-d₂ was injected in the awake animal 30 min prior to MRI acquisition.

Brain DDG-d₂ distribution observed using a CSI-SSFP sequence with the following parameters: TR/TE = 15.5/1.2 ms, matrix 8×8, FOV 30×30 mm, single slice thickness 12 mm, 64 spectral points, and 1209 averages (acquisition time 16 min 32 s). The estimated contrast-to-noise ratio is 32.

References.

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